

SECTION I ACTUAL PROBLEMS OF TEACHING LANGUAGE IN XXI CENTURY'S CONDITIONS

CHALLENGES IN LANGUAGE TEACHING IN THE 21ST CENTURY, THE INFLUENCE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ON LANGUAGE LEARNING AND TEACHING

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Abstract:

Nowadays, language teaching faces countless challenges and opportunities. Globalization, technological advancements and changing societal needs have reshaped the approach to teaching and learning. Furthermore, the recent emergence and advancement of artificial intelligence (AI) has introduced new possibilities for language acquisition and instruction, as well as potential areas of opportunity. This article aims to explore current issues in language teaching in the 21st century, with a particular focus on the influence of AI on language learning. By examining the intersection of these two domains, we seek to gain insights into the evolving dynamics of language education and the potential for AI to reshape traditional teaching.

Key words: language teaching, globalization, technological advances, artificial intelligence, language learning, AI applications, and chatbots

doi: <https://doi.org/10.2024/y667y942>

The term "artificial intelligence" (AI) is not new since its history dates back to the 1950s when Alan Turing proposed in his book *Computing Machinery and Intelligence* "Whether machines can think intelligently, and how we could determine whether a machine is capable of exhibiting true intelligence (Turing, 1950)." Over more than 70 years, AI has experienced periods of advancement and stagnation, but in recent decades, it has gained momentum due to technological advances since they have made it accessible to the majority of the population.

Currently, the use of technology and the massive integration of AI in various sectors, such as health, education and transportation, pose challenges in terms of regulation and governance, especially for young people, as for them, it represents a way of accessing information of any kind quickly and efficiently, This poses a series of challenges that require attention and innovative solutions.

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International Conference

HUMANISTIC ROLE OF LANGUAGE AND LITERATURE IN THE CONTEMPORARY GLOBALIZATION

In the field of education, especially in language teaching, the integration of technology as a learning tool has been considered essential since the 1980s, when the use of language laboratories became popular due to the accessibility of personal computers. This brought endless opportunities in educational matters; in the case of language teaching, it allowed the development of specific linguistic skills such as auditory and verbal, increasing the overall experience of students by allowing them access to different accents and regionalisms specific to each language.

However, the emergence and popularity of artificial intelligence tools such as ChatGPT, have caused an interdependence among students, although AI provides teaching and learning resources, it lacks personalization and the ability to adapt to the needs of students, which can limit effectiveness in language learning and generate codependency on AI itself to generate texts, answer questions and translate.

Excessive dependence on AI in students goes beyond just generating texts or translating since it can produce several cognitive risks, such as problem-solving considering that they may obtain information immediately, normally without analyzing it, students may tend to not solve problems on their own, which could limit their ability to think critically and find creative solutions, Miller proposes (1956) in his information processing theory that “ Humans actively process the information they receive from the environment. and that learning occurs through interaction with this information.” According to this theory and if applied to the field of education, students participate in cognitive processes such as attention, perception, memory and thinking while interacting with information. Excessive dependence on AIs could limit these active interactions, turning them into passive recipients of information instead of active participants in the learning process.

This echoes Piaget's (1966) cognitive learning theory which focuses on how individuals acquire and process information, focusing on processes such as memory, thinking and reasoning. According to this theory, learning is an active process in which students construct their own knowledge by interacting with information and relating it to their previous experiences. That is, accepting the information provided by AI without the use of critical thinking would compromise their own learning process.

These theories show that excessive dependence, without regulation or pedagogical guidance on AI, could hinder the cognitive development of students by limiting their active participation in the learning process, their ability to construct knowledge in a meaningful way, and their interaction with others.

Despite the aforementioned challenges, the regulated use of AI brings with it a significant number of opportunities for both students and teachers, since it reduces the time of tutorial planning and, development of evaluation questionnaires and rubrics.

According to Blanka's Klimova and Dr Prodhana Mahbub Ibna Seraj's (2023) article “The use of chatbots in university EFL settings: Research trends and pedagogical implications”. The use of AI-based chatbots has had various effects on students' performance in learning different linguistic skills since an improvement has been demonstrated in terms of intonation, emphasis and fluency, as increased participation of students in developing better oral expression skills inside and outside the classroom and it was observed that those with more basic linguistic skills benefited more from the use of chatbots.

The same study mentions the implementation of AI chatbots in the classroom as a tool for both teachers and students in the learning and teaching of different linguistic skills, they provide a student-controlled environment by incorporating dialogue, voice recognition, and comprehension of natural language that have helped improve conversational skills, these tools have been used to evaluate the linguistic skills of students within the Common European Framework of Reference (CEFR).

In conclusion, the use of artificial intelligence is transforming the educational landscape, especially in the field of language learning. Some studies have shown a significant impact on the development of students' language skills, improving fluency, pronunciation and classroom participation. In addition, they offer new opportunities for exposure and practice for both teachers and students, creating a more dynamic and participatory learning environment. However, clear policies are required regarding the use and limitations of its application in classrooms.

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